

TEACHING GUIDE

Gender-Sensitive Computer Science Education

Despite various interventions in the education sector, girls* remain underrepresented in computer science (CS) classes [3, 4]. With CS set to become a mandatory subject in Hamburg schools in the 2025/26 school year, promoting gender equity and motivating girls* in CS education is increasingly important. This guide supports CS teachers in creating classrooms where all students, regardless of their gender, feel equally involved and included. Based on key research findings [3, 4, 8], four broad categories of measures are outlined below and will be specified in more detail. The measures and their individual strategies often overlap and can have mutually reinforcing effects. While many of the strategies in this guide contribute to improving CS education for all students, they are especially important for addressing the specific needs of girls* and creating an environment where they feel welcome and confident.

The asterisk after girls* signals that gender is not limited to two categories. It includes those who don't identify strictly as "female" or "male" and highlights gender and identity diversity.

Challenging Stereotypes

Challenging stereotypes is key to gender-sensitive computer science teaching. CS is still often associated with “nerdy boys” while girls* are frequently seen as lacking interest or ability in STEM disciplines. Addressing these stereotypes is crucial to prevent girls* from feeling discouraged by the image of computer science or losing confidence in their abilities. Teachers play a vital role in this process—their awareness and attitude toward existing inequalities are essential. This includes reflecting on their own biases and considering how these might influence their teaching. It's also important to actively address stereotypes in class, examine them with students, and work to prevent their reinforcement.

Adopting a Gender-Sensitive Teaching Approach

	Strategies	Goals
	Professional training in gender-sensitive teaching <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Through self-study, school conferences, or external training programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing awareness of stereotypes and inequalities Gaining confidence in addressing them
	Self-reflection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibly with a guided questionnaire and peer support (e.g., with the guideline of the <i>Amt für Lehrerbildung</i> [1]) Impulses for reflection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there qualitative or quantitative differences in teacher-student interactions between girls and boys? Do girls have the same access to and time with technology as boys? Do girls participate equally in classroom activities? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognizing one’s own stereotypical thought and behavior patterns Acknowledging both girls and boys equally in class Developing fair and gender-aware assessment practices
	Gender-inclusive language <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address both girls and boys equally Mention both female and male computer scientists (or other professions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively encouraging and including girls Strengthening girls’ sense of belonging
	Clear classroom rules <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No (derogatory) comments Sanction discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying, discussing, and stopping discriminatory language and behavior

Case Study: Discrimination in Computer Science Class

In their study, Spieler and Girvan [8] describe a classroom activity where students discuss their experiences with computer science and their gaming preferences. The authors observe the following situation:

All the boys mentioned computer games (e.g., FIFA, Sonic), while the girls mostly referred to mobile games (e.g., Candy Clash, Quiz Duel). The boys laughed at the girls' responses and showed a lack of focus. [translated from German]

The boys' behavior creates a dismissive atmosphere that can make the girls feel belittled, not taken seriously, and consequently less motivated to participate. It also reinforces discriminatory stereotypes (e.g., that girls are less interested or competent in technology) and enforces persistent gender inequality in CS. This situation calls for decisive teacher intervention. The boys' laughter should be clearly labeled as disrespectful and unacceptable, while the girls should be encouraged to continue to share their contributions.

As a preventive measure, it's helpful to establish classroom behavior rules early on and collaboratively define what respectful communication looks like. In cases of repeated dismissive or offensive behavior, these rules should be reiterated to the class, and appropriate consequences should be applied to uncooperative students.

Gender-Sensitive Teaching Materials

Strategies	Goals
<p>Reflecting on students' perceptions of computer science as a class topic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do students associate with computer science? • Who works in the field? • What do people in computer science do? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Uncovering stereotypes ➤ Showing the diversity within the field
<p>Teaching the history of computer science with a focus on diversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight diverse contributions from people of different backgrounds • Including women, and individuals from varied ethnic, cultural, racialized, or social groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Promoting a realistic and inclusive view of the field's history ➤ Challenging stereotypical role models
<p>Using gender-sensitive textbooks, images, and worksheets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender parity: representing all genders equally and fairly • Avoid stereotypical gender portrayals • Use names and examples that reflect students' real-life contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Breaking down gender stereotypes ➤ Representing students' identities and engaging them

What Not to Do: Gender-*Insensitive* Teaching Material

Various websites on the subject of encryption feature this or similar illustrations:

The chosen example for key exchange draws on a long-standing tradition in computer science and cryptography, where security scenarios are illustrated using the characters *Alice* and *Bob*. However, an uncritical adoption of this convention—especially in educational contexts—is problematic from a gender-sensitive perspective.

Criticism

- **Reinforcement of gender stereotypes**
 - *Alice* is shown with long red hair, a pink top, and earrings; even her key is pink – she embodies common, clichéd traits of femininity or “womanhood”
 - *Bob* wears glasses, has short dark hair, and is dressed in a plain, functional outfit – a neutral presentation that aligns with a rational, competent male stereotype in a technical context
 - This contrast reinforces stereotypical ideas: *Girls = emotional, playful, decorative* vs. *Boys = rational, technically skilled*
- **Lack of diversity**
 - Only two binary, stereotyped gender roles are depicted: a “typical” woman and a “typical” man
 - There is no diversity in skin tone, clothing, or non-binary identities
 - Especially in gender-sensitive teaching materials, it is important to make diversity visible so that all learners can find points of identification

Suggestions for Improvement

- Use **gender-neutral or non-traditional representations** (such as neutral colors, unconventional color pairings, symbols or abstract / non-human figures) at least as frequently as conventional gender imagery
- Avoid rigid, stereotypical color associations such as pink for women and grey/beige for men – instead, aim for **balanced and varied use of colors and symbols**
- Increase **diversity in visual representations**: for example, include a range of skin tones, clothing styles, hairstyles, and gender-neutral or non-binary figures
- Be intentional about role and competence representation:
 - Who is acting?
 - Does *Alice* have a problem and *Bob* solves it, or are both equally capable and active?
- **Move beyond the *Alice-Bob* convention**:
 - Use more diverse names and characters to promote representation
 - Choose names that reflect the socio-cultural backgrounds of the students
- **Openly discuss gender stereotypes in teaching materials**
 - It's not always possible to create your own visuals or find gender-sensitive materials for every topic
 - When using existing, potentially problematic materials:
 - Address in class which names and role models are presented and how they shape our perception

Creating a Safe Learning Environment

To ensure that all students feel equally safe and encouraged to participate, ask questions, and experiment in computer science class, it's important to shape both the social and physical environment in ways that strengthen their sense of safety and belonging. Gender-sensitive teaching emphasizes cooperation, openness to mistakes, and equal opportunity.

Social Environment and Social Learning Structures

Strategies	Goals
<p>Working in Teams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pair and group work • Grouping students by experience level or by gender 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Creating a sense of safety ➤ Increasing participation and engagement ➤ Providing more teacher time for less experienced students ➤ Working in preferred group constellations
<p>Sufficient time for tasks and questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students learn at their own pace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reducing pressure in class ➤ Actively encouraging questions
<p>“Growth mindset” and openness to mistakes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treat mistakes as valuable learning opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reducing student fears ➤ Building confidence
<p>No competition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on collaborative problem-solving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reducing social and performance pressure ➤ Avoiding performance hierarchies

CS Classroom Design

Strategies	Goals
<p>Group and pair work tables</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid single desks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Enabling various cooperative learning formats (see above)
<p>Diversity-sensitive classroom decorations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posters of female computer scientists • Information or posters on CS projects that support or are tailored to girls • Avoid science-fiction-themed decor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Strengthening girls' sense of belonging and identification with CS ➤ Representing the diversity and reality of computer science ➤ Countering the “nerd”-stereotype
<p>Display classroom projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e.g., microcontrollers or robots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sparking sustained interest ➤ Fostering students' sense of agency

	Find helpful links for posters and materials in the appendix.	p. 12f
---	---	--------

Exemplary Design of a Gender-Sensitive Computer Science Classroom

- Desk arrangement supports cooperation and collaboration in groups and tandems
- The teacher's desk and a large screen for presentations are placed at the front of the room
- Empty walls are decorated with subject-relevant posters
 - Posters of female computer scientists to emphasize equality and diversity in CS
 - *Important:* posters should feature both female and male computer scientists
 - Posters about programs supporting girls in CS, *here:* a "Girls' Day" poster, which informs girls about interesting events and participation opportunities
- A large shelf at the front displays current or past classroom projects (e.g., robots)
- Science fiction themes and stereotypically male-coded gaming machines are avoided in the room

Promoting Long-Term Interest

To promote lasting interest in computer science, students' curiosity and motivation must be actively and consistently supported. This is most effective when they experience early and repeated small successes, recognize the subject's relevance to their own lives and society at large, and regularly get the chance to collectively reflect and share their experiences. These findings are true for both girls and boys. For this reason, a core goal of gender-sensitive CS education is to ease access to the subject and connect it meaningfully to girls' everyday lives. This helps build and maintain long-term interest.

Lowering Entry Barriers to CS

Strategies	Goals
<p>Playful and creative introductions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graphic programming with Scratch: Develop games and animations based on girls' interests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Offering a low-threshold, playful entry point ➤ Including student interests in lesson plans ➤ Strengthening students' self-efficacy and confidence through quick wins by creating simple programs
<p>Introductory lesson plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> e.g., using IT2School materials by Wissensfabrik 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Introducing students to topics through playful, problem-oriented, and discovery-based approaches
<p>Computer science without computers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> e.g., with lesson plans from CS Unplugged 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Conveying core CS concepts through hands-on and playful methods ➤ Reaching and encouraging students with no or limited prior experience or confidence with technology or computers

Making CS Relevant to Students' Lives

Strategies	Goals
<p>Cross-curricular lessons to show real-world relevance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> e.g., intoMINT: an app introducing girls to cross-disciplinary STEM topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Motivating girls through real-life projects ➤ Covers e.g. encryption, 3D modeling, cryptocurrency, chatbots [2]
<p>Incorporating students' interests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Let students choose project topics based on their everyday experiences Example for OOP: instead of library systems, let students code a music playlist, adventure game, or pet-care app 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Making lessons participatory and student-centered ➤ Strengthening identification with and sense of belonging in CS

Addressing the social impact of CS

- Use real-world examples and case studies: data privacy scandals, algorithmic biases, social networks, fake news, etc.
 - Invite or attend guest talks
- Emphasizing the relevance of CS content and skills
 - Exploring the role of computing in students' everyday lives

Strengthening Girls' Sense of Agency

Strategies	Goals
<p>Hands-on experiences with physical computing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of microcontrollers, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Calliope mini ○ Arduino ○ BBC micro:bit • A wide range of ready-to-use lesson plans and teacher trainings on microcontroller programming is available online, e.g. [7] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Making CS concepts tangible through immediate results ➤ Reducing fear of technology ➤ Enabling practical, creative projects with real-world relevance where girls can implement their own ideas
<p>Project- and product-based learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students create usable final products in class, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Their own apps [5, 6], e.g. using MIT App Inventor 2 ○ Podcasts or explainer videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Allowing girls to experience success in creating functional products through their own actions ➤ Allowing students to bring in their own interests and creativity while developing their own ideas

Creating Space for Reflection

Strategies	Goals
<p>Encourage reflection and open discussion of classroom experiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively and regularly (not just once) gather student feedback on tasks, progress, and topics • Offer multiple reflection formats: exit tickets, think-pair-share, lightning rounds, reflection journals, emoji charts, etc. • For sensitive topics, allow anonymity: suggestion box, digital survey tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Getting to know students better ➤ Regularly gauging class atmosphere ➤ Supporting students constructively ➤ Fostering an open and respectful classroom climate ➤ Enabling active participation and creating space for trust

Building a Realistic Image of Computer Science

In addition to challenging gender stereotypes and clichéd notions in computer science, it is essential that students develop a realistic understanding of the field. For girls in particular, learning about the wide range of careers and roles in computer science is especially important, as traditional gender roles and the typical association of tech fields with boys and men often hinder their identification with the subject and their self-image. A key task of gender-sensitive teaching is therefore to replace stereotypical images by introducing role models and building networks that offer girls authentic insights and positive points of reference.

	Strategie	Ziel
	Establish CS clubs for girls <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create early exposure to computer science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Providing a safe, pressure-free learning space ➤ Supporting long-term interest
	Introduce mentoring or buddy systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect older female students with younger beginners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Strengthening sense of belonging ➤ Reducing (social) anxiety ➤ Encouraging peer support among girls
	Include (female) role models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer or promote girls-for-girls courses • Cooperate with educational initiatives, companies, and universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Strengthening sense of belonging ➤ Boosting self-confidence ➤ Sparking lasting interest ➤ Connecting girls with female role models

	Find helpful links to CS projects for girls* in the appendix.	p. 14f
---	---	--------

References

- [1] Amt für Lehrerbildung (AfL), Ed. 2009. *Handreichung Förderung von gendersensibler Medienbildung. Genderaspekte in der Medienbildung; didaktische Materialien zum Einsatz in europäischer Lehrerbildung*, Frankfurt am Main.
- [2] Bade, K., Böhnke, S., Marschik, G., and Scheidat, T. 2021. Die intoMINT App als Einstieg in die Informatik. In *INFORMATIK*, Gesellschaft für Informatik (GI), Ed., Bonn.
- [3] Gesellschaft für Informatik. 2017. „*Informatik ist etwas für Mädchen!*“. *Maßnahmen für eine erhöhte Repräsentation von Mädchen im Informatikunterricht*.
- [4] Happe, L., Buhnova, B., Koziolk, A., and Wagner, I. 2021. Effective measures to foster girls' interest in secondary computer science education. *Educ Inf Technol* 26, 3, 2811–2829.
- [5] Kreinsen, M., Thiems, M., Sprenger, S., & Schulz, S. (2024). A project-based AI and Data Education Concept for STEM Teacher Education in Teaching-Learning-Labs. In *Proceedings of DELFI 2024* (pp. 10-18420). Gesellschaft für Informatik eV.
- [6] Kreinsen, M., Thiems, M., Sprenger, S., & Schulz, S. (2024). Interdisciplinary AI and Data Lab in Teacher Education: Teaching-Learning Material. University of Hamburg. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12063386>
- [7] Lindner, Marlene, Sandra Schulz, and Niels Pinkwart. "Integration des Erwerbs von Basiskonzepten der Informatik in den mathematisch-naturwissenschaftlichen Unterricht der Sekundarstufe I." *Informatische Bildung zum Verstehen und gestalten der digitalen Welt*. 2017.
- [8] Spieler, B. and Girvan, C. 2020. Das PECC-Framework. Gender-Sensibilität und spielerische Programmierung in der informatischen Grundbildung. In *Die 18. Fachtagung Bildungstechnologien (DELFI), Lecture Notes in Informatics (LNI)*, R. Zender, Ed., Bonn.

Appendix

	<h2 style="margin: 0;">Helpful Links and Resources</h2>
---	---

Diversity-Sensitive Posters and Materials for the Classroom

Initiative / Project	Description	Link
Kompetenzzentrum Materialcenter <i>(only in German)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central contact point for all „Kompetenzzentrum“ projects • Offers materials and various free posters to order or download • Relevant projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Girls' Day ○ Initiative Klischeefrei, ○ Komm, mach MINT ○ #FrauWirktDigital 	https://material.kompetenzz.net
Komm, mach MINT <i>(only in German)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • „Auf in neue Welten“ - Computer Science Poster • DIN A1 poster for STEM career orientation 	https://material.kompetenzz.net/komm-mach-mint/schuelerinnen/auf-in-neue-welten-informatik-plakat-a-1.html
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • „Heldinnen der Informatik“- Poster • DIN A1 poster 	https://material.kompetenzz.net/komm-mach-mint/schuelerinnen/plakat-heldinnen-der-informatik.html
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer Science Brochure about Careers in IT • Female computer scientists talk about their careers, fields of work, and what computer science is about 	https://material.kompetenzz.net/komm-mach-mint/schuelerinnen/informatikerinnenbroschuere.html
#FrauWirktDigital <i>(only in German)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offers decorative postcards featuring important women in computer science (e.g., Grace Hopper, Ada Lovelace, Margaret Hamilton) for download 	https://material.kompetenzz.net/fwd

English Resources

Teaching Computing

London

- A project by CAS London supporting teachers in computer science locally and globally
- Offers various resources, including posters (in English)

Poster collection: Women in Computing:

<https://teachinglondoncomputing.org/women/>

Poster collection: Diversity in Computing:

<https://teachinglondoncomputing.org/celebrating-diversity-in-computing/>

Code.org

- Educational initiative to make computer science accessible to all students
- Offers a selection of relevant posters (in English).

General site: <https://code.org/en-US/about>

Posters for the classroom:

<https://code.org/en-US/resources/classroom-posters>

Projects Supporting Girls* in Computer Science

Initiative / Project	Description	Link
mint:pink	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives middle school girls insight into practical applications of STEM subjects and careers in science and technology • Activities include company visits, scientific institutions, and a speed dating event with female role models in STEM • Participation through school cooperation 	https://mintforum.de/angebote/angebot/mintpink
GIRLS Hacker School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT courses where girls can try out programming and the creative IT world in a safe space 	https://hacker-school.de/formate/girls-hacker-school/
Einstieg Informatik	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides information for teens interested in computer science, including leisure activities, study options, and careers • Offers a community area for networking and joint projects • Features an overview page for projects and events specifically for girls 	https://www.einstieg-informatik.de/tag/maedchen/

Other Exciting Computer Science Projects for All Students

Initiative / Project	Beschreibung	Link
MINTforum Hamburg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A network for projects, initiatives, and institutions in STEM education • Connects stakeholders from daycare, schools, universities, public authorities, businesses, and foundations • Offers an event calendar with filters for computer science topics 	https://mintforum.de/terminkalender?filterMintTag=false&selectedAgeFrom&selectedAgeTo&selectedDistrict&selectedSubject=2&selectedTargetGroup
Codeweek Hamburg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offers free workshops and hands-on events every fall for children, teens, and adults 	https://hamburg.codeweek.de/